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Geological habitat template overrides late Quaternary climate change as a determinant of range dynamics and phylogeography in some habitat-specialist water beetles

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Short running head: Range dynamics and phylogeography in habitat-specialist species

ABSTRACT

Aim We investigated the roles of lithology and climate in constraining the ranges of four co-distributed species of Iberian saline-habitat specialist water beetles (*Ochthebius glaber*, *Ochthebius notabilis*, *Enochrus falcarius* and *Nebrioporus baeticus*) across the late Quaternary and in shaping their geographical genetic structure. The aim was to improve our understanding of the effects of past climate changes on the biota of arid Mediterranean environments and the relative importance of history and landscape on phylogeographical patterns.

Location Iberian Peninsula, Mediterranean.

Methods We combined species distribution modelling (SDM) and comparative phylogeography. We used a multi-model inference and model-averaging approach both for assessment of range determinants (climate and lithology) and for provision of spatially explicit estimates of the species' current and Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) potential ranges. Potential LGM distributions were then contrasted with the phylogeographical and population expansion patterns as assessed using mitochondrial DNA sequence data. We also evaluated the relative importance of geographical distance, habitat resistance and historical isolation for genetic structure in a causal modelling framework.

Results Lithology poses a strong constraint on the distribution of Iberian saline-habitat specialist water beetles, with a variable, but generally moderate additional influence by climate. The degree to which potential LGM distributions were reduced and fragmented decreased with increasing importance of lithology. These SDM-based suitability predictions were mostly congruent with phylogeographical and population genetic patterns across the study species, with stronger geographical structure in genetic diversity of the more temperature-sensitive species (*O. glaber* and *E. falcarius*). Furthermore, while historical isolation was the only factor explaining genetic structure

in the more temperature-sensitive species, lithology-controlled landscape configuration also played an important role for those species with more lithology-determined ranges (*O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus*).

Main conclusions Our data show that lithology is an important constraint on the distribution and range dynamics of endemic Iberian saline-habitat water beetles, in interaction with climate and long-term climate change, overriding the latter in importance for some species. Hence, geological landscape structure and long-term history may codetermine the overall range and the distribution of genetic lineages in endemic species with specialized edaphic requirements.

Keywords

Coleoptera, demographic history, habitat connectivity, hindcasting, Iberian Peninsula, landscape genetics, Last Glacial Maximum, Mediterranean, saline inland waters, species distribution modelling.

INTRODUCTION

The dramatic climate changes of the Quaternary, particularly the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) approximately 21 ka (thousand years ago), have influenced the demographic history, genetic diversity, and distribution of many species (Hewitt, 2000). In Europe, research on this topic has focused on arctic–alpine and forest species (Schmitt, 2007). As a result, the role of Quaternary climatic fluctuations in other environments remains less understood. This is in large part true for arid Mediterranean lowlands (but cf. Muñoz *et al.*, 2008; Pérez-Collazos *et al.*, 2009; Ortego *et al.*, 2009) and in particular for their inland saline aquatic ecosystems, which are globally restricted to arid lands and in Europe only occur in the Mediterranean region (Williams, 2002). While inland saline aquatic ecosystems house high numbers of endemic species (Millán *et al.*, 2011), little is known about which factors determine their ranges and genetic diversity patterns.

Although climate is often assumed to be the main range-limiting factor (Gaston, 2003; Pearson & Dawson, 2003), other abiotic factors can prevent species from occupying climatically suitable areas (Gaston, 2003). In inland saline aquatic systems, environmental constraints are imposed by both climatic and geological conditions (Williams, 2002; Millán *et al.*, 2011). In Europe, natural inland saline aquatic ecosystems are associated with specific lithological conditions (Millán *et al.*, 2011), notably calcareous and evaporitic outcrops. Hence, for species requiring such saline habitats, geological substrate is likely to be an important range constraint.

As a consequence of these climatic and geological constraints, inland saline environments in the western Mediterranean are highly fragmented. Hence, taxa inhabiting them may be particularly influenced by the landscape structure (Abellán *et al.*, 2007; Ortego *et al.*, 2009, 2010). Previous phylogeographical studies of saline-habitat specialist water beetles (Abellán *et al.*, 2007, 2009) have revealed contrasting patterns of genetic structure among species, perhaps reflecting differential

impacts of landscape structure (distribution of habitat patches) and past climatic events. Landscape genetic approaches have most often been used to examine how current spatial features influence contemporary levels of connectivity and divergence among populations (Storfer *et al.*, 2010). Applying similar methods in a historical framework provides insights into the population-level processes that underlie phylogeographical patterns and how they have changed over time (Chan *et al.*, 2011).

In this study we combine species distribution modelling (SDM; Elith & Leathwick, 2009) and comparative phylogeography for four co-distributed species of Iberian saline-habitat specialist water beetles to investigate the roles of lithology and climate in constraining their ranges across the late Quaternary and in shaping their genetic structure. Our specific hypotheses were threefold. (1) Lithology forms an important range constraint for Iberian saline-habitat water beetles. (2) Species for which lithology is the dominant present-day range constraint have not been affected by the glacial–interglacial climate changes (i.e., they have had a relatively static range and population size during the late Quaternary); in contrast, species whose present-day ranges are greatly affected by current climate have experienced population and range expansion since the LGM. (3) In the former species, phylogeographical structure mainly reflects habitat connectivity; in contrast, in the latter species, with contracted, disjunct LGM ranges, phylogeographical structure mainly reflect these refugia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study species

We focus on four species of water beetles of inland saline environments in the Iberian Peninsula: *Ochthebius glaber* Montes & Soler, *Ochthebius notabilis* Rosenhauer, *Nebrioporus baeticus*

(Schaum), and *Enochrus falcarius* (Hebauer). All are restricted to saline and hypersaline waters and represent characteristic macroinvertebrates of this habitat in the Iberian Peninsula (Millán *et al.*, 2011). *Ochthebius glaber* is restricted to hypersaline streams in the south of the Iberian Peninsula. *Ochthebius notabilis* is found across the Iberian Peninsula and northern Africa (Jäch, 1992), inhabiting stagnant water bodies. *Nebrioporus baeticus* is distributed from the south of the Iberian Peninsula to the Pyrenees, occurring in saline streams. Finally, *Enochrus falcarius* has traditionally been viewed as a species widely distributed across the western Mediterranean. However, a recent study has revealed that this species as currently understood actually comprises a complex of different lineages, with small allopatric distributions (Arribas *et al.*, in press). Here, we focused on the Iberian lineage of this species complex (“*E. falcarius* IP” *sensu* Arribas *et al.*, in press, here *E. falcarius* for simplicity), restricted to saline streams in the southern Iberian Peninsula.

Species distribution modelling

We used SDM to investigate the relative role of current climate and lithology in constraining the distribution of the four species, as well as to estimate their present and past (LGM) distributions as a basis for explaining geographical patterns in their genetic diversity.

Occurrence data and predictor variables

Occurrence data were compiled from previous studies (Abellán *et al.*, 2009; Arribas *et al.*, in press) as well as from intensive recent sampling of inland saline habitats across the Iberian Peninsula (A. Millán *et al.*, unpublished data). Occurrence localities for the different species represent most (if not all) known Iberian populations (see Fig. 1 and Table S1 in Appendix S1 in Supporting Information).

For the present-day SDM we initially considered the 19 bioclimatic variables from the WorldClim dataset at a spatial resolution of 2.5' (<http://www.worldclim.org/>; Hijmans *et al.*, 2005). For the LGM (*c.* 21 ka) we used climate reconstructions of the same 19 bioclimatic variables based on two general atmospheric circulation models (GCM): the Community Climate System Model (CCSM; Collins *et al.*, 2006) and the Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate (MIROC v. 3.2; Hasumi & Emori, 2004) from the Paleoclimate Modelling Intercomparison Project Phase II (PMIP2) made available via WorldClim. To avoid multicollinearity problems, only a single variable from sets of highly correlated variables ($r > 0.9$) was used in the modelling, leaving a final set of 10 climatic predictor variables (Table 1). To account for geological range constraints, we additionally used lithology (dominant parent material) derived from the European Soil Database v2 (Van Liedekerke *et al.*, 2006) as a categorical predictor variable, encompassing 43 different categories of geological material in the Iberian Peninsula.

Modelling algorithm, model selection, and multi-model inference and prediction

We modelled species distributions using the maximum-entropy machine-learning SDM algorithm Maxent v. 3.3.3e (Phillips & Dudík, 2008). Maxent is applicable to presence-only data and is considered among the most accurate SDM algorithms (Elith *et al.*, 2006). To avoid basing our results solely on a single distribution modelling algorithm, we performed supplementary analyses using the Mahalanobis distance approach (MD; Farber & Kadmon, 2003). MD ranks potential sites by their Mahalanobis distance to a vector expressing the mean environmental conditions (the centroid) of all the species' records in the environmental space, and it requires neither absence data nor a definition of study extent.

We were interested in the relative performance of models with only climatic predictors compared to those also including lithology. Hence, two different models were calibrated for each

species with Maxent: one using the 10 selected climatic predictors, and the other one additionally including lithology as a categorical predictor. We then assessed the support for these sets of predictors using several approaches to evaluate model performance. The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) was computed using Maxent's internal validation procedure in order to evaluate predictive ability of each model (Phillips & Dudík, 2008). Although AUC is widely used to estimate the predictive accuracy in SDM, recent studies have highlighted limitations, especially with regards to its application to presence-only data (e.g., Lobo *et al.*, 2008). An additional and important issue concerning model performance in SDM is model complexity: Maxent may overfit species-predictor relationships, especially with small sample sizes, and overfitting will induce underprediction when the distribution model is applied to new climatic scenarios (Warren & Seifert, 2011). In Maxent, model complexity is constrained via regularization, which allows users to constrain over-parameterization by specifying a regularization multiplier parameter (β) that penalizes addition of parameters (Phillips & Dudík, 2008). Warren & Seifert (2011) have shown the utility of information-theoretic approaches for setting regularization in Maxent, demonstrating that criteria such as AIC (Akaike's information criterion) may offer significant advantages. We computed different Maxent models by varying the regularization multiplier parameter (from 0.5 to 4) and allowed feature types (product, linear, quadratic, hinge and threshold; Phillips & Dudík, 2008). In all, we therefore obtained 72 different models (36 with only climatic predictors and 36 with both climatic variables and lithology; Table S2) for each species. We assessed the relative support for each model using sample-size-corrected AIC (AIC_c) (Burnham & Anderson, 1998), using ENMTools (Warren *et al.*, 2010). We then obtained a confidence set of models for each species: each model's AIC_c was rescaled (ΔAIC_c) by subtracting the minimum AIC_c value in the model set, i.e., the best model has $\Delta AIC_c = 0$ (Burnham & Anderson, 1998). Models with $\Delta AIC_c > 10$ were discarded, as having essentially no support (Burnham & Anderson, 1998).

We also excluded models with more parameters than data points (which violate the assumptions of AIC_c ; Warren & Seifert, 2011). Akaike weights were then used to measure the probability that a given model was the best model for the observed data within the set of candidate models (Burnham & Anderson, 1998). We then used a multi-model inference and model-averaging approach for both assessment of range determinants and for providing spatially explicit estimates of the species' current and LGM potential ranges, i.e., areas with suitable environmental conditions. Multi-model-average relative contribution (%) of each environmental predictor in the Maxent distribution models for each species was assessed by averaging its influence across the confidence set of models, weighted by Akaike weight. Potential-range predictions were likewise obtained by averaging predictions across the confidence set of models, weighted by Akaike weight; hereby, we reduced model bias and accounted for model uncertainty (Burnham & Anderson, 1998).

The supplementary Mahalanobis distance analyses were performed on the final model variable sets from the Maxent analyses for each species (Table 1) using the Mahalanobis distances ArcView extension (Jenness, 2003). Lithology was transformed into presence/absence of potentially saline substrates (marls and evaporitic rocks). The Mahalanobis distances were converted into probability values, rescaling to range 0–1 according to the χ^2 distribution (Farber & Kadmon, 2003).

Model-averaged LGM predictions under CCSM and MIROC simulations were obtained as described above; with a subsequent averaging across the final CCSM and MIROC predictions. Because geology is unlikely to have changed significantly since the LGM, we treated lithology as constant.

To obtain binary predictions for the present and LGM to be used in the phylogeographical analyses, we converted the averaged, continuous Maxent outputs into presence/absence predictions

using maximum training sensitivity plus specificity thresholding, which has been found to perform well compared to other thresholding methods (Liu *et al.*, 2005).

Phylogeographical analyses

Genetic data

Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) sequences (3' end of cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1, COI) for the four species were obtained from previous studies (Abellán *et al.*, 2007, 2009; Arribas *et al.*, in press; P. Arribas *et al.*, unpublished results). A total of 342 sequenced specimens of *O. glaber* (90), *E. falcarius* (72), *N. baeticus* (93) and *O. notabilis* (87) were used, covering their known geographical ranges with a mean of five individuals per locality (see Table S1; GenBank accession numbers for sequences of *E. falcarius* are indicated in Table S3).

Genetic diversity, population structure and haplotype relationships

Standard genetic diversity indices were estimated using DNASP v. 5 (Librado & Rozas, 2009). Genetic differentiation between populations with ≥ 4 sequenced individuals was quantified by pairwise Φ_{ST} and tested for significance by 10,000 permutations using ARLEQUIN v. 3.5 (Excoffier & Lischer, 2010).

Potential LGM distributions were contrasted with the phylogenetic relationships among mtDNA haplotypes. Networks of the mitochondrial COI haplotypes for *E. falcarius* were inferred using statistical parsimony using TCS v. 1.13 (Clement *et al.*, 2000), while networks for *O. glaber*, *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus* were taken from Abellán *et al.* (2009).

Analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA; Excoffier *et al.*, 1992) was used to assess the partitioning of genetic variation among and within biogeographical regions as represented by the main Iberian river basins (see Fig. 2). AMOVAs were performed using ARLEQUIN, using 10,000 permutations. Individual collecting localities were treated as populations.

Estimating variation in effective population size over time

We tested for post-glacial range expansions using two genetic approaches, for comparison with SDM-based estimates of range stasis or expansion.

The demographic history of every biogeographical region (with ≥ 10 individuals) for each species was inferred based on mismatch distributions of pairwise nucleotide differences (Rogers & Harpending, 1992) with 1000 bootstrap replications in ARLEQUIN. The goodness of fit between the observed and expected distributions of demographic models, including sudden expansion and spatial expansion, was calculated using sum of square deviations (SSD; Schneider & Excoffier, 1999). The raggedness index (r) of the observed mismatch distribution was also calculated for each of the populations and its significance determined similar to SSD as implemented in ARLEQUIN. Non-significant deviations of expected and observed mismatch distributions and low raggedness values would indicate past population expansion (Rogers & Harpending, 1992). For expanding populations, tau (τ ; calculated from the mismatch distribution; see Schneider & Excoffier, 1999) was used to estimate time since expansion (t) using the equation $\tau = 2\mu t$, where μ is the neutral mutation rate for the locus (Schneider & Excoffier, 1999). The confidence intervals for τ were calculated using parametric bootstrap (Schneider & Excoffier, 1999). Divergence rates for COI in Coleoptera range 3.34–4.00% (Papadopoulou *et al.*, 2010; Ribera *et al.*, 2010). We used the average of these values (3.62% Myr⁻¹), and assumed a 1-year generation time.

Tajima's D (Tajima, 1989) and Fu's F_s (Fu, 1997) are sensitive to departures from mutation-drift equilibrium due to population size changes (expansions, bottlenecks) and selection, and were computed for the biogeographical regions using ARLEQUIN. Significant negative deviations of these indexes from zero are interpreted either as evidence of selective sweeps or population expansions (Fu, 1997).

Testing landscape and historical effects on genetic structure

The SDM estimates of potential ranges were also used to directly test alternative phylogeographical scenarios. The genetic structure in species of limited dispersal ability inhabiting patchy habitats might be expected simply to reflect geographical distance among habitat patches. Alternatively, landscape characteristics may influence gene flow between populations by affecting dispersal rates and the spatial arrangement among them. Such landscape effects may be represented by resistance surfaces that assign different resistance-to-movement values to different landscape features (Storfer *et al.*, 2010). If such landscape effects have been important, we would expect a positive relationship between genetic distance and landscape resistance, after controlling for geographical distance or history (see below). We estimated landscape resistance by inverting the SDM estimates of habitat suitability (Chan *et al.*, 2011), accounting for changes across time by estimating resistance for both LGM and the present. Matrices of resistance distances among population pairs were computed with the software CIRCUITSCAPE v. 2.2 (McRae & Shah, 2009), which uses circuit theory to evaluate total landscape resistance between sampling sites based on multiple paths.

If historical isolation in biogeographical regions (main river basins) during the late Quaternary has played a major role in shaping genetic structure, we expect strong genetic differentiation between them after controlling by geographical distance or landscape characteristics.

Historical geographical structure was represented by a matrix, where locality pairs were assigned a value of 1 if in the same region, and 0 otherwise.

We then evaluated the relative importance of geographical distance, habitat resistance and historical isolation for genetic structure using Mantel tests and partial Mantel tests in a causal modelling framework (Cushman *et al.*, 2006). We identified the diagnostic expectations for each hypothesis of causal relationships (Table 2). Thus, the model with best support should exhibit not only the highest simple correlation with genetic distance, but also a significant, positive partial correlation with genetic distance after controlling for each competing factor. Mantel tests and partial Mantel tests were computed in the R software v. 2.13 (R Development Core Team, 2011) using the ‘vegan’ package (Oksanen *et al.*, 2007), with significance assessed using 10,000 permutations.

RESULTS

Species distribution models

The Maxent models for all species provided strong support for the joint importance of climate and lithology (Table 3). For *E. falcarius*, *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus*, confidence sets comprised only models that included both climate and lithology, because all models with only climatic predictors had essentially no support ($\Delta\text{AIC}_c > 10$; Table S2). For *O. glaber*, two strictly climatic models were included among the 12 models in the confidence set, but only with 0.3–3.2% support (Table S2). For those models with the highest support for each species, the probability that they were the best model for the observed data according to Akaike weights was always lower than 40%. In all cases, these most probable models included both climate and lithology (see Table S2). Models including lithology had significantly higher training AUC values than those including only climatic variables,

as assessed by t-tests (*O. glaber*, $t = 6.92$, $P < 0.001$; *E. falcarius*, $t = 11.43$, $P < 0.001$; *O. notabilis*, $t = 9.08$, $P < 0.001$; *N. baeticus*, $t = 10.16$, $P < 0.001$; see also Table 3).

In all species, multi-model inference identified lithology as the most important range predictor, with a high relative contribution (50–89%), with climate also providing an important contribution except in *N. baeticus* (Table 1). Among climatic variables, mean temperature of driest quarter had highest relative contribution in *O. glaber*, *E. falcarius* and *N. baeticus* (although accounting for only a 6% of relative contribution in this last species), while precipitation of the driest quarter was the most important climatic variable in *O. notabilis* (Table 1). Hence, temperature only plays a major role for *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius*.

In general, the multi-model average Maxent predictions matched reported species distributions (Figs 1–2). The models also predicted suitable conditions outside their reported distribution, especially in central Spain for *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius* and to the north-west of their current distribution for *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus*.

Projecting these models to the LGM, the estimated distributions did not differ dramatically from the present day, although the temperature-sensitive *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius* displayed markedly lower overall habitat suitability (Figs 1–2). Suitable areas were more fragmented and discontinuous at LGM for all species, but especially for two temperature-sensitive species, notably in terms of reduced continuity between their current main areas of distribution.

The Mahalanobis distance modelling provided predictions that were consistent with the Maxent results for both the present and LGM (Fig. S1), with potential ranges for *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius* mainly restricted to southern Iberia and more fragmented than those for *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus*, especially at the LGM.

Phylogeographical structure and demographic changes

Genetic diversity was higher in the Guadalquivir basin (southern Iberia) than in the other regions for all species (Table 4). AMOVA analyses detected significant genetic structuring among populations grouped by the main river basins of the Iberian Peninsula in the four species (Table 5). The proportion of overall variance accounted for by differences among regions differed markedly among species, being especially high for temperature-sensitive *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius*. Hence, these species had regional groups that were genetically relatively different from each other and internally more homogeneous than the other species. The least climatically sensitive species, *N. baeticus* provided the strongest contrast, with genetic differences within populations accounting for the highest proportion of variance. Correspondingly, haplotype networks in *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius* showed clear geographical structure with mostly no shared haplotypes among the main river basins; haplotype networks in *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus* showed more complex patterns, with shared haplotypes among some regions and high levels of homoplasy (Fig. 2).

Negative and significant Fu's F_S were obtained for nearly all the regions (excluding those with small sample sizes) and species (Table 4). These values represented significant departures from those expected under a null model of demographic equilibrium and genetic drift. With respect to Tajima's D , although most regions showed negative values, these were significant only in Guadalquivir basin for *E. falcarius* and *N. baeticus*. The mismatch distributions were mostly not significantly different from those expected under either a spatial expansion or a sudden demographic expansion (Table 4; see also Table S4 and Fig. S2). The estimated time at which these expansions occurred for the different regions in each species were variable, but all in the late Quaternary (Table 4).

Landscape and historical effects on genetic structure

In all species, genetic distance (pairwise Φ_{ST} , Table S5) had significant correlations to all tested spatial factors (Euclidean distance, habitat resistance at both the present and LGM, main river basin regions; Table 6). However, in the temperature-sensitive *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius* genetic distance was most strongly correlated with river basins, corresponding to long-term isolation in these regions (see Fig. 2). Furthermore, in these species the other spatial factors had no importance after controlling for the river basin effect. In contrast, present habitat connectivity (see Fig. S3) had the strongest relationship with genetic distance in *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus* (although river basin regions had similar correlations). Interestingly, in these species the correlation between genetic distance and present habitat resistance was markedly stronger than for habitat resistance at the LGM. Most importantly, it was only in these species that habitat resistance was significantly correlated with genetic distance after controlling for both geographical distance and the river basin region effect. Nevertheless, *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus* also exhibited significant river basin region effects after controlling for the other factors.

According to the causal modelling framework (Table 2), the hypothesis of historical isolation in river basin regions was the only fully supported one for *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius*, while in *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus* the hypothesis of isolation by both habitat resistance and main regions was the only fully supported one.

DISCUSSION

By integrating species distribution modelling with phylogeography, we can derive a more refined image of driving forces that have led to the distributions of extant taxa and their genetic diversity (Kozak *et al.*, 2008; Svenning *et al.*, 2011). Our data show that lithology poses an important

constraint on the distribution and range dynamics of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles, with climate playing a variable, but more moderate role. We furthermore find that long-term history (linked to climate history) and geological habitat template interact in shaping geographical genetic structure, with the former being more important for the species with more temperature-sensitive ranges and habitat template more important for species with more lithology-controlled ranges.

Predicted distributions, range dynamics and phylogeography

Species distribution models have become a common tool in studies of biogeography, conservation biology, ecology, evolutionary biology, and palaeobiology (Elith & Leathwick, 2009; Svenning *et al.*, 2011). Improving model selection, model evaluation and predictor contribution assessment are central challenges in the development of SDM (Elith & Leathwick, 2009). Here, we explore some of these issues: models for prediction need to balance fit to the training data against generality that enables reliable prediction to new cases (Elith & Leathwick, 2009). Although model complexity is not usually addressed, it can influence the ability of the model to assess the relative importance of variables in constraining species' distributions, predict suitable habitat suitability, and the transferability to other time periods (Warren & Seifert, 2011). Our results show that Maxent models produced with default parameter settings were in many cases too complex, because they included more parameters than data points (Table S2), revealing that default regularization parameters do not always prevent Maxent from overfitting. The fact that predictions obtained with Mahalanobis distance were similar to those estimated using Maxent indicate our SDM-based findings are not algorithm dependent. Importantly, in contrast to Maxent, the Mahalanobis distance method relies exclusively on presences (i.e., it does not use pseudo-absences from “background” environmental data) and is not extent dependent. Hence, the congruence between the two modelling techniques

suggests that past potential distributions estimated by the averaged Maxent models do not represent overfit or biased estimates.

The first aim of this study was to assess the relative role of climate and lithology for saline-habitat water beetles species distributions. Our results show that non-climatic environmental factors such as lithology can be important not only at local scales (Thuiller *et al.*, 2004), but also at regional scales in habitat-specialist species (see also e.g., Gastón *et al.*, 2009): distributions of all four water beetles are importantly limited by lithology, with > 50% relative contribution in all species. In contrast, climatic factors only moderately influence distributions. Moreover, among climatic predictors, temperature only plays a major role for *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius*.

As a consequence of the limited influence of climate, inferred LGM distributions were not dramatically different from present-day distributions, although overall suitability was always reduced (Fig. 1). These findings suggest that species were able to persist throughout much of their current ranges during the late Pleistocene, with cold episodes (such as LGM) mainly leading to diffuse population contraction. There is strong palynological (González-Sampériz *et al.*, 2010), biogeographical (Ribera & Blasco-Zumeta, 1998) and phylogeographical (Pérez-Collazos *et al.*, 2009) evidence supporting the persistence of suitable areas across the Iberian Peninsula for steppe and arid biota throughout the Pleistocene. Arid conditions were not interrupted during this period, at least in the Guadalquivir and Ebro Basins (Plans, 1969), and different phylogeographical studies that focused on saline invertebrates suggest a scenario of persistence in multiple Iberian suitable areas (Gómez *et al.*, 2000; Ortego *et al.*, 2009; Pérez-Collazos *et al.*, 2009). For *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius*, climatic changes increased isolation among their main areas of occurrence (river basins). In contrast, ranges of *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus* are predicted to have remained more stable.

The SDM suitability predictions were mostly congruent with the genetic patterns. Both parsimony haplotype networks and AMOVA analyses revealed a strong geographical structure in the temperature-sensitive *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius*, in agreement with SDM-predicted historical isolation in their main areas of occurrence (Avice, 2000). The absence of shared haplotypes and the high genetic differentiation among regions coupled with low genetic differentiation among populations within regions, point to a scenario in which gene flow has been very restricted (Abellán *et al.*, 2007, 2009). Although AMOVA analyses also supported that mtDNA haplotype variation is partitioned among the main Iberian regions in *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus*, groups were less genetically homogeneous, and haplotype networks exhibited more complex geographical patterns, suggesting some gene flow among regions and the additional role of other factors (see below).

If ranges were more restricted in the past as consequence of cold episodes, subsequent post-glacial range expansions must have been associated with demographic expansion (e.g., Lessa *et al.*, 2003). This was supported by the results of the mismatch distribution analysis. Although mismatch distribution analysis may have little power (Ramos-Onsins & Rozas, 2002), the indices Tajima's D and Fu's F_S also suggested population growth. The star-shaped pattern in the haplotype networks for *E. falcarius* and *O. glaber* in some regions also point to either rapid population expansion from a refugium or founder events (Avice, 2000), although at variable times during the late Quaternary, partially pre-LGM (Table 4). On the other hand, and despite the fact that paleoclimatic reconstructions point to a history of greater stability in habitat patches in *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus*, we also found footprints of demographic expansion in most regions for these species, in agreement with the moderate overall reduction in suitability predicted for these species (Fig. 1). Nevertheless, time estimates again suggest pre-LGM demographic events. Hence, the latitudinal decrease of genetic diversity in all four species may reflect northward colonization events from

southern Iberia and, ultimately, North Africa, with subsequent population growth (Pérez-Collazos *et al.*, 2009).

Effects of history and landscape on genetic structure

The causal modelling framework allowed further assessment of which factors determine genetic structure (Cushman *et al.*, 2006), disentangling effects of long-term history and geological landscape structure. In concordance with the phylogeographical and population genetic results, we found contrasting influences of the different spatial factors in the four species. Our findings show that historical river-basin structure plays an important role in explaining the genetic differentiation and population structure in all four species, in agreement with results for Iberian endemic fish (Gómez & Lunt, 2007) and other Iberian saline invertebrates (Gómez *et al.*, 2000; Ortego *et al.*, 2009, 2010). Nevertheless, while this historical component was the only factor explaining genetic structure in the temperature-sensitive *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius* after removing the other effects of spatial factors, landscape configuration also played a crucial independent role in *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus*.

The different phylogeographical patterns and the contrasting role of historical and landscape factors in shaping genetic structure in *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius* versus *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus* seems to be consequence of their differential climatic sensitivity, perhaps coupled with differences in dispersal ability. Despite the fact that the four studied species are all able to fly, little is known regarding their dispersal. Dispersal ability for *O. glaber* seems to be limited, as suggested by its high degree of geographical genetic structure (Abellán *et al.*, 2007). In fact, differences in dispersal ability have already been suggested for explaining differences in phylogeography between *O. glaber* and *O. notabilis* (Abellán *et al.*, 2009), which occur in saline habitats with contrasting long-

term stability (running and standing water bodies, respectively). Similarly, a recent study suggests reduced dispersal capability in *E. falcarius* in relation to its relatives inhabiting standing waters (Arribas *et al.*, unpublished results).

The impact of barriers to dispersal and gene flow is often inferred to be the primary cause of phylogeographical structure (Aise, 2000). All barriers ultimately represent regions of unsuitable ecological conditions for a species, reducing dispersal and affecting range limits (Gaston, 2003). According to the framework proposed by Pyron & Burbrink (2010), the differences in the phylogeographical patterns found between both species pairs in relation to spatial factors could represent two contrasting modes of geographical isolation: physically mediated (“hard”) and ecologically mediated (“soft”) allopatric divergence. While in *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius* divergence would be a consequence of barriers representing discrete physiographic features – associated with unfavourable climatic conditions – limiting dispersal (e.g., Steeves *et al.*, 2005), divergence in *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus* would be a consequence of their response to more continuously varying ecological conditions (e.g., Costa *et al.*, 2008). So, the configuration of the actual Iberian river basins represents a main factor generating barriers and isolating populations in *O. glaber* and *E. falcarius*, with isolation increased during Pleistocene cold episodes, reflecting their limited dispersal capacity coupled with higher sensitivity to climatic conditions (see also Sánchez-Fernandez *et al.*, 2011). In the putatively more vagile *O. notabilis* and *N. baeticus*, physiographical features and geological landscape configuration would represent hierarchical spatial-temporal drivers (e.g., Kosciński *et al.*, 2009).

CONCLUSIONS

By exploring our data with an integrative approach, it was possible to reveal how climate and climatically-driven historical fluctuations in population demography, and associated historical isolation, and geological habitat template interact to shape distributions and phylogeographical patterns in Iberian saline-habitat specialist water beetles. Our results emphasize the importance of multifaceted approaches combining ecological and genetic modelling to obtain improved insights into the determinants of range dynamics and phylogeography, as well as, more broadly, for assessing the effects of Quaternary climatic fluctuations on European biodiversity. Furthermore, from a conservation perspective, by identifying long-term barriers to gene flow, and contrasting effects of climate and landscape on genetic diversity, it will be possible to model species responses to future environmental changes more realistically.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of this article:

Appendix S1 Additional data and results (Tables S1–S5 and Figures S1–S3).

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Table 1 Multi-model-average relative contribution (%) of environmental predictors in the Maxent distribution models for each of the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles, assessed by averaging the influence of each variable in the confidence set of models, weighted by Akaike weight.

Variable	<i>Ochthebius glaber</i>	<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	<i>Ochthebius notabilis</i>	<i>Nebrioporus baeticus</i>
Lithology	49.96	59.89	69.81	88.68
Mean temperature of the driest quarter	32.22	22.78	0.00	5.96
Precipitation of the driest quarter	1.73	10.50	23.56	1.67
Annual precipitation	3.14	0.47	5.91	0.27
Annual mean temperature	7.45	1.75	0.00	0.03
Isothermality	3.13	0.63	0.00	0.60
Temperature annual range	1.44	0.13	0.00	1.12
Mean temperature of the wettest quarter	0.43	0.00	0.01	0.00
Minimum temperature of the coldest month	0.12	0.00	0.04	0.02
Maximum temperature of the warmest month	0.08	3.60	0.00	0.00
Precipitation seasonality	0.02	0.27	0.62	1.70

Table 2 Causal modelling framework for phylogenetic inference for Iberian saline-habitat water beetles based on genetic diversity. Diagnostic expectations (partial Mantel test and expected significance value) for each hypothesis, D (Euclidean distance), H (Habitat resistance), R (Historical regions, long-term isolation in main river basins), G (Genetic distance): NS, not significant; > 0, significant positive correlation ($P < 0.05$); NA, not applicable. A period separates the main matrices on the left from the covariate matrix on the right that is controlled for in the partial Mantel test. For example, DG.H is a partial Mantel test between geographical and genetic distance after controlling for habitat resistance.

Test	Models and diagnostic expectations						
	Geographical distance	Habitat resistance	Historical regions	Distance and Habitat	Distance and regions	Habitat and regions	Distance, habitat, regions
DG.H	> 0	NS	NA	> 0	> 0	NS	> 0
DG.R	> 0	NA	NS	> 0	> 0	NS	> 0
HG.D	NS	> 0	NA	> 0	NS	> 0	> 0
HG.R	NA	> 0	NS	> 0	NS	> 0	> 0
RG.H	NA	NS	> 0	NS	> 0	> 0	> 0
RG.D	NS	NA	> 0	NS	> 0	> 0	> 0

Table 3 Comparisons of the predictive ability and model support among species distribution models for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles, based on two different set of predictors (climate and climate plus lithology). AUC, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve for training data; ΣW , summed Akaike weights.

Species	Model set	AUC	ΣW (%)
<i>Ochthebius glaber</i>	Climate	0.924 (0.885-0.974)	3.67
	Climate + Lithology	0.955 (0.920-0.982)	96.33
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	Climate	0.920 (0.886-0.981)	~ 0
	Climate + Lithology	0.970 (0.954-0.990)	~ 100
<i>Ochthebius notabilis</i>	Climate	0.749 (0.635-0.928)	~ 0
	Climate + Lithology	0.879 (0.820-0.948)	~ 100
<i>Nebrioporus baeticus</i>	Climate	0.796 (0.719-0.923)	~ 0
	Climate + Lithology	0.904 (0.873-0.954)	~ 100

Table 4 Genetic diversity, demographic statistics and mismatch distribution results for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles in the different regions. n , sample size; π , nucleotide diversity; h , number of haplotypes; H , haplotype diversity; D , Tajima's D -test and F_S , Fu's F_S -test (bold: P -value < 0.05); $P(\text{SDD})$, P -value for the sum of the squared deviations under the hypothesis of spatial expansion; $P(\text{Rag})$, P -value for the raggedness index (regions with samples sizes < 10 sequences are not shown). Tau (τ) was converted to thousand years ago (T , in ka) as an estimate of the time of expansion. CI, confidence interval. Main Iberian river basins: GUA, Guadalquivir; SEG, Segura; JUC, Júcar; EBR, Ebro; GUD, Guadiana; TAJ, Tajo.

Region	n	π	h	H	F_S	D	spatial expansion model			
							$P(\text{SSD})$	$P(\text{Rag})$	τ (95% CI)	T (ka)
<i>Ochthebius glaber</i>										
GUA	42	0.014	27	0.970	-14.094	-1.014	0.596	0.896	6.8 (5.1-9.8)	117 (87-168)
SEG	32	0.004	14	0.791	-4.202	-0.914	0.765	0.852	2.9 (1-6.1)	50 (18-104)
JUC	16	0.002	7	0.775	-3.228	-1.025	0.521	0.429	1.4 (0.6-2.3)	24 (10-39)
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>										
GUA	42	0.003	18	0.664	-3.877	-1.625	0.67	0.601	2.6 (0.3-5.1)	45 (6-88)
SEG	24	0.001	5	0.529	-1.350	-0.916	0.045	0.283	0.6 (0.3-1.4)	10 (5-24)
JUC	6	0.001	2	0.533	0.625	0.851	--	--	--	--
<i>Ochthebius notabilis</i>										
GUA	23	0.005	13	0.874	-5.751	-1.413	0.79	0.881	3.6 (1.3-5.3)	62 (23-92)
SEG	5	0.001	2	0.600	0.626	1.225	--	--	--	--
JUC	7	0.002	3	0.524	0.541	-0.876	--	--	--	--
EBR	21	0.004	9	0.757	-3.868	-0.684	0.600	0.729	2.7 (0.8-4.2)	46 (14-72)
GUD	5	0.001	2	0.400	0.090	-817	--	--	--	--
TAJ	7	0.004	2	0.476	2.508	0.755	--	--	--	--
<i>Nebrioporus baeticus</i>										
GUA	42	0.005	20	0.950	-14.530	-1.571	0.645	0.826	2.9 (1.9-4.7)	50 (33-81)
SEG	16	0.003	9	0.917	-4.130	-0.931	0.402	0.323	2.2 (1-3.2)	39 (17-55)
JUC	6	0.000	1	0.000	--	--	--	--	--	--
EBR	23	0.004	7	0.798	0.162	0.180	0.811	0.843	3.6 (1.2-6.3)	62 (21-109)
GUD	2	0.000	1	0.000	--	--	--	--	--	--
TAJ	13	0.000	1	0.000	--	--	--	--	--	--

Table 5 Results of the AMOVA analyses with individuals of the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles grouped by main regions (river basins) and populations. The percentage of total variance and *P*-value (in parentheses) are shown.

	<i>Ochthebius glaber</i>	<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	<i>Ochthebius notabilis</i>	<i>Nebrioporus baeticus</i>
Among regions	83.26 (< 0.001)	50.65 (< 0.001)	42.11 (< 0.001)	36.83 (< 0.001)
Among populations within regions	6.10 (< 0.001)	7.42 (0.005)	28.78 (< 0.001)	16.44 (< 0.001)
Within populations	10.63 (< 0.001)	41.93 (< 0.001)	29.15 (< 0.001)	46.74 (< 0.001)

Table 6 Mantel and partial Mantel correlations (r) between spatial and genetic pairwise distances of the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles among localities (bold: P -value < 0.05). D, Euclidean distance; H_p, habitat resistance at the present; H_{LGM}, habitat resistance at the Last Glacial Maximum; R, Regions (historical isolation in main river basins); G, genetic distance.

Test	<i>Ochthebius glaber</i>		<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>		<i>Ochthebius notabilis</i>		<i>Nebrioporus baeticus</i>	
	r	P -value	r	P -value	r	P -value	r	P -value
DG	0.704	0.000	0.518	0.002	0.391	0.002	0.294	0.001
H _p G	0.664	0.000	0.525	0.002	0.542	0.000	0.386	0.004
H _{LGM} G	0.621	0.000	0.524	0.003	0.387	0.010	0.272	0.022
RG	0.836	0.000	0.802	0.000	0.531	0.000	0.351	0.000
DG.H _p	0.317	0.002	0.107	0.156	-0.094	0.217	0.124	0.061
DG.H _{LGM}	0.489	0.000	0.080	0.221	0.129	0.140	0.116	0.075
DG.R	0.097	0.141	-0.071	0.257	0.135	0.123	0.046	0.290
H _p G.D	0.054	0.359	0.147	0.114	0.417	0.010	0.288	0.028
H _{LGM} G.D	-0.270	0.007	0.123	0.157	0.112	0.289	0.009	0.466
H _p G.R	0.096	0.213	-0.171	0.120	0.451	0.006	0.222	0.034
H _{LGM} G.R	0.016	0.424	-0.125	0.175	0.291	0.057	0.057	0.343
RG.H _p	0.682	0.000	0.723	0.000	0.435	0.003	0.144	0.009
RG.H _{LGM}	0.714	0.000	0.719	0.001	0.476	0.002	0.238	0.000
RG.D	0.638	0.000	0.718	0.000	0.409	0.005	0.207	0.001

Figure legends

Figure 1 Species distribution modelling predictions for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles for the present (left) and the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM, right) obtained with Maxent. Warmer colours represent areas of higher habitat suitability. Black points represent present-day occurrence data used in the modelling. The percentage of the summed habitat suitability at the LGM relative to the present is also indicated. The insert shows the position of the study area in the Mediterranean Basin.

Figure 2 Comparison between present and Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) potential ranges and phylogenetic relationships among mtDNA haplotypes of the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles (statistical parsimony networks). Shaded areas correspond to suitable areas: dark grey, stable areas (i.e., suitable during both time periods); light grey, present distributional areas predicted to have been unsuitable during the LGM; and black, currently unsuitable areas predicted to have been suitable during the LGM. The boundaries of the main river basins are indicated by green lines. Populations used in genetic analyses are shown in the maps with colour circles (different colours represent the different main regions: blue, Guadalquivir; orange, Segura; green, Júcar; red, Ebro; yellow, Guadiana; purple, Tajo). In COI haplotype networks, solid lines connect haplotypes with a single step (missing intermediates are indicated by small open circles). Circle diameter is proportional to the number of individuals. White haplotypes in *Ochthebius notabilis* correspond to Moroccan populations.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Geological habitat template overrides late Quaternary climate change as a determinant of range dynamics and phylogeography in some habitat-specialist species

Pedro Abellán, Paula Arribas and Jens-Christian Svenning

Journal of Biogeography

Appendix S1 Additional data and results (Tables S1–S5 and Figures S1–S3)

Table S1 Localities used for species distribution modelling for each of the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles and populations included in the genetic analyses in this study. Asterisks indicate localities used in species distribution models but not in the genetic analyses. Codes for the main regions are as in Table 4.

CodeLoc	Locality	Region	Longitude	Latitude
<i>Ochthebius glaber</i>				
CAD	Salinas de Hortales, Cádiz	GUA	-5.54	36.74
COR1	Ayo. Salinas de Duernas, Córdoba	GUA	-4.6	37.7
COR2	Salinas de la Maturra, Córdoba	GUA	-4.36	37.68
COR3	Río salado de Priego, Córdoba	GUA	-4.18	37.41
JAE1	Ayo. Salinas de Brujuelo, Jaén	GUA	-3.67	37.89
JAE2	Arroyo de las Salinas de Porcuna, Jaén	GUA	-4.22	37.79
JAE3	Salinas de Chíllar, Hinojares, Jaén	GUA	-3.00	37.71
ALI2	Estrecho de la Salineta, Alicante	SEG	-0.78	38.43
ALI3	Rambla de Albaterra, Alicante	SEG	-0.95	38.24
MUR2	Rambla de Sangonera, Murcia	SEG	-1.29	37.95
MUR5	Rambla Salada de Fortuna, Murcia	SEG	-1.12	38.13
MUR8	Rambla de la Parra, Murcia	SEG	-1.07	38.2
MUR9	Ayo. Salinas de la Ramona, Murcia	SEG	-1.62	38.21
MUR10	Rambla de Librilla, Murcia	SEG	-1.37	37.91
VAL1	Ayo. hipersalino en R. Gabriel, Valencia	JUC	-1.3	39.34
CUE3	Rambla de Minglanilla1, Cuenca	JUC	-1.57	39.56
CUE4	Rambla de Minglanilla2, Cuenca	JUC	-1.57	39.56
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>				
SEV1	Arroyo del Peinado. Osuna	GUA	-5.17	37.23
SEV2	Arroyo Montero. Montellano	GUA	-5.69	36.98
CAD	Salinas de Hortales, arroyo. El Bosque	GUA	-5.54	36.74
COR1	Salinas de Duernas. El Espejo	GUA	-4.60	37.70
COR2	Salinas de la Maturra, arroyo. Baena	GUA	-4.36	37.68
COR3	Río Salado. Priego de Córdoba	GUA	-4.18	37.41
GRA	Salinas de Malahá. Malahá	GUA	-3.72	37.10
JAE1	Salinas de Brujuelo, arroyo. Brujuelo	GUA	-3.67	37.89
JAE2	Salinas de Porcuna, arroyo. Valenzuela	GUA	-4.22	37.79
JAE4	Arroyo Salado. Siles	GUA	-2.55	38.41
ALI1	Rambla de Algüeda. Albaterra	SEG	-0.90	38.25
MUR1	Rambla de Agua Amarga. Cieza	SEG	-1.50	38.31
MUR11	Río Chícamo. Abanilla	SEG	-1.05	38.22
MUR2	Salinas de Sangonera, arroyo. Murcia	SEG	-1.29	37.95
MUR3	Rambla del Reventón. Mazarrón	SEG	-1.37	37.64
MUR4	Rambla del Pozo de En medio. Caravaca	SEG	-1.98	37.89
MUR5	Rambla Salada. Fortuna	SEG	-1.14	38.14
CUE4	Arroyo Salado. Minglanilla	JUC	-1.56	39.55
<i>Ochthebius notabilis</i>				

CAD	Salinas de Hortales, Cádiz	GUA	-5.54	36.74
COR1	Ayo. Salinas de Duernas, Córdoba	GUA	-4.6	37.7
COR2	Salinas de la Maturra, Córdoba	GUA	-4.36	37.68
GRA	Salinas de Malahá, Granada	GUA	-3.72	37.1
JAE1	Ayo. Salinas de Brujuelo, Jaén	GUA	-3.67	37.89
JAE3	Salinas de Chfllar, Hinojares, Jaén	GUA	-3	37.71
SEV2	Ayo. Montero, Sevilla	GUA	-5.69	36.98
HUV1*	Salinas de Odiel, Huelva	GUA	-6.99	37.25
HUV2*	Estero de la Sardina, Ayamonte, Huelva	GUA	-7.43	37.25
CAD2*	Salinas de San Fernando, Cádiz	GUA	-6.21	36.46
HUV3*	Marismas del Guadalquivir, Brazo de la Torre, Huelva	GUA	-6.25	37.00
FAR1*	Salinas de Faro, Portugal	GUA	-7.96	37.01
JAE4*	Ayo salado entre Cotillas y Siles	GUA	-2.55	38.41
ALI2*	Rambla del Estrecho de la Salineta	SEG	-0.78	38.43
MUR7	Salinas del Zacatín, Murcia	SEG	-2.12	38.2
ALB1	Salinas de Pinilla, Albacete	GUD	-2.62	38.84
ALB2	Manantial en Casas de Ves, Albacete	JUC	-1.28	39.29
CUE1	Ayo. en Salinas del Manzano, Cuenca	JUC	-1.56	40.09
GUA3*	Salinas de Imón	TAJ	-2.73	41.16
CUE2	Salinas de Valsalobre, Guadalajara	TAJ	-1.9	40.82
GUA1	Salinas Alcolea de las Peñas, Guadalajara	TAJ	-2.79	41.22
GUA4	Salinas Saelices de la Sal , Guadalajara	TAJ	-2.33	40.9
HUE	Salinas de la Rolda, Naval , Huesca	EBR	0.15	42.19
LER	Salinas Gerri de la Sal, Lérida	EBR	1.07	42.33
TER1	Ayo hipersalino en Arcos de las Salinas, Teruel	EBR	-1.06	39.99
ALA	Salinas de Añana, Álava	EBR	-2.99	42.8
BUR	Salinas Poza de la Sal, Burgos	EBR	-3.5	42.67

Nebrioporus baeticus

CAD	Ayo. Salinas de Hortales, Cádiz	GUA	-5.54	36.74
COR1	Ayo. Salinas de Duernas, Córdoba	GUA	-4.6	37.7
COR2	Ayo. Salinas de la Maturra, Córdoba	GUA	-4.36	37.68
COR3	Río Salado de Priego, Córdoba	GUA	-4.18	37.41
GRA	Ayo. Salinas de Malahá, Granada	GUA	-3.72	37.1
JAE1	Ayo. Salinas de Brujuelo, Jaén	GUA	-3.67	37.89
JAE2	Arroyo de las Salinas de Porcuna, Jaén	GUA	-4.22	37.79
SEV1	Arroyo El Peinado, Osuna, Sevilla	GUA	-5.17	37.23
SEV2	Ayo. Montero, Sevilla	GUA	-5.69	36.98
JAE4*	Ayo salado entre Cotillas y Siles	GUA	-2.55	38.41
ALI1	Rbla. de Algüeda, Albaterra, Alicante	SEG	-0.9	38.25
MUR1	Rambla de Agua Amarga, Murcia	SEG	-1.5	38.31
MUR2	Rambla de Sangonera, Murcia	SEG	-1.29	37.95
MUR3	Rambla del Reventón, Murcia	SEG	-1.37	37.64
MUR4	Rambla Pozo Enmedio, Murcia	SEG	-1.98	37.89
MUR5	Rambla Salada de Fortuna, Murcia	SEG	-1.12	38.13

ALB1	Ayo. Salinas de Pinilla, Albacete	GUD	-2.62	38.84
CUE1	Ayo. en Salinas del Manzano, Cuenca	JUC	-1.56	40.09
CUE2	Ayo. Salinas de Valsalobre , Cuenca	TAJ	-1.9	40.82
GUA1	Ayo. Salinas Alcolea de las Peñas, Guadalajara	TAJ	-2.79	41.22
GUA2	Ayo. Salinas O. de Jadraque , Guadalajara	TAJ	-2.74	41.13
GUA3	Ayo. Salinas de Imon, Guadalajara	TAJ	-2.73	41.16
GUA4	Ayo. Salinas Saelices de la Sal, Guadalajara	TAJ	-2.33	40.9
NAV1	A. Bardenas Blancas (El Yugo), Navarra	EBR	-1.61	42.25
NAV2	Barranco Salado de Mendavia, Navarra	EBR	-2.15	42.42
NAV3	R. salado de Valtierra, F.Eguara, Navarra	EBR	-1.64	42.17
ZAR1	A. Salino Mediana de Aragón, Zaragoza	EBR	-0.74	41.46
ZAR2	Bco. Salado Zuera, Zaragoza	EBR	-0.76	41.88
HUE	Ayo. Salinas de la Rolda, Naval , Huesca	EBR	0.15	42.19
ALA	Ayo. Salinas de Añana, Álava	EBR	-2.99	42.8

Table S2 Comparison of species distribution models of the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles based on different sets of predictors (climate or climate and lithology) and varying model complexity. β , regularization multiplier parameter of Maxent; LL , model log likelihoods; k , number of free parameters (k); ΔAIC_c , rescaled Akaike information criterion; W , Akaike weights; AUC, area under the curve of a receiver operating characteristic plot. The feature types used in Maxent in each model are also indicated (l, linear; q, quadratic; p, product, t, threshold; h, hinge). “Auto features” indicates that Maxent was allowed to choose the set of features based on the size of the training data set to build the prediction. Asterisks indicate models included in the final confidence sets. Models for which AIC_c values are not shown correspond to models with more parameters than data points (which violate the assumptions of AIC_c).

Model	β	l	q	p	t	h	LL	k	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	W (%)	AUC	
<i>Ochthebius glaber</i>													
Climate	0.5	Auto features					-133.87	33					0.970
Climate	0.5	x					-154.01	5	323.47	14.00	0.0345	0.915	
Climate	0.5	x	x				-148.66	8	331.32	21.85	0.0007	0.931	
Climate	0.5	x	x	x			-150.49	7	327.42	17.95	0.0048	0.929	
Climate	0.5	x	x	x	x		-129.10	23				0.961	
Climate	0.5	x	x	x	x	x	-127.78	33				0.974	
Climate	1	Auto features					-141.93	20				0.954	
Climate	1	x					-155.53	5	326.51	17.04	0.0076	0.909	
Climate	1	x	x				-152.44	8	338.89	29.42	0.0000	0.92	
Climate	1	x	x	x			-153.61	5	322.67	13.20	0.0514	0.921	
Climate*	1	x	x	x	x		-142.72	8	319.45	9.98	0.2580	0.941	
Climate	1	x	x	x	x	x	-139.77	22				0.956	
Climate	1.5	Auto features					-146.78	15	803.56	494.09	0.0000	0.945	
Climate	1.5	x					-156.78	4	324.90	15.43	0.0169	0.907	
Climate	1.5	x	x				-154.14	8	342.28	32.81	0.0000	0.917	
Climate	1.5	x	x	x			-155.58	4	322.48	13.01	0.0565	0.916	
Climate*	1.5	x	x	x	x		-147.00	6	314.40	4.93	3.2149	0.936	
Climate	1.5	x	x	x	x	x	-144.71	15	799.41	489.94	0.0000	0.95	
Climate	2	Auto features					-150.03	11	374.86	65.39	0.0000	0.936	
Climate	2	x					-158.08	4	327.49	18.02	0.0046	0.907	
Climate	2	x	x				-155.45	5	326.36	16.89	0.0081	0.914	
Climate	2	x	x	x			-157.53	4	326.39	16.92	0.0080	0.913	
Climate	2	x	x	x	x		-152.39	7	331.22	21.75	0.0007	0.928	
Climate	2	x	x	x	x	x	-149.21	13	445.76	136.29	0.0000	0.943	
Climate	3	Auto features					-155.82	10	368.31	58.84	0.0000	0.919	
Climate	3	x					-161.74	3	331.34	21.87	0.0007	0.902	
Climate	3	x	x				-158.52	4	328.38	18.91	0.0030	0.907	
Climate	3	x	x	x			-161.36	4	334.06	24.59	0.0002	0.907	
Climate	3	x	x	x	x		-161.36	4	334.06	24.59	0.0002	0.907	
Climate	3	x	x	x	x	x	-155.80	11	386.41	76.94	0.0000	0.927	
Climate	4	Auto features					-160.46	8	354.91	45.44	0.0000	0.906	

Climate	0.5	x								-164.02	6	347.68	30.35	0.0000	0.905
Climate	0.5	x	x							-160.82	7	346.85	29.52	0.0000	0.918
Climate	0.5	x	x	x						-160.97	7	347.13	29.81	0.0000	0.923
Climate	0.5	x	x	x	x					-141.25	25				0.970
Climate	0.5	x	x	x	x	x				-137.28	36				0.981
Climate	1	Auto features								-151.41	22				0.956
Climate	1	x								-165.63	5	346.26	28.93	0.0000	0.898
Climate	1	x	x							-163.78	6	347.20	29.87	0.0000	0.907
Climate	1	x	x	x						-163.02	6	345.67	28.34	0.0000	0.917
Climate	1	x	x	x	x					-156.07	9	352.63	35.31	0.0000	0.94
Climate	1	x	x	x	x	x				-150.71	20				0.956
Climate	1.5	Auto features								-156.57	12	399.55	82.22	0.0000	0.945
Climate	1.5	x								-166.62	5	348.24	30.92	0.0000	0.896
Climate	1.5	x	x							-165.02	7	355.25	37.92	0.0000	0.902
Climate	1.5	x	x	x						-164.72	5	344.45	27.12	0.0000	0.913
Climate	1.5	x	x	x	x					-159.95	7	345.10	27.77	0.0000	0.932
Climate	1.5	x	x	x	x	x				-157.07	17				0.945
Climate	2	Auto features								-160.36	9	361.23	43.90	0.0000	0.935
Climate	2	x								-167.78	4	346.64	29.31	0.0000	0.896
Climate	2	x	x							-166.24	5	347.48	30.16	0.0000	0.898
Climate	2	x	x	x						-165.99	5	346.98	29.66	0.0000	0.912
Climate	2	x	x	x	x					-163.18	7	351.55	34.22	0.0000	0.924
Climate	2	x	x	x	x	x				-160.49	14	488.97	171.65	0.0000	0.936
Climate	3	Auto features								-165.19	10	381.80	64.48	0.0000	0.913
Climate	3	x								-170.73	4	352.53	35.21	0.0000	0.894
Climate	3	x	x							-168.30	5	351.61	34.28	0.0000	0.894
Climate	3	x	x	x						-168.53	4	348.13	30.80	0.0000	0.909
Climate	3	x	x	x	x					-168.52	4	348.12	30.80	0.0000	0.909
Climate	3	x	x	x	x	x				-165.27	11	396.55	79.22	0.0000	0.922
Climate	4	Auto features								-169.70	5	354.40	37.07	0.0000	0.897
Climate	4	x								-174.18	3	356.08	38.75	0.0000	0.886
Climate	4	x	x							-170.44	4	351.96	34.64	0.0000	0.893
Climate	4	x	x	x						-171.27	3	350.26	32.93	0.0000	0.905
Climate	4	x	x	x	x					-171.27	3	350.26	32.93	0.0000	0.905
Climate	4	x	x	x	x	x				-170.48	7	366.16	48.83	0.0000	0.904
Climate+Lithology	0.5	Auto features								-132.12	28				0.985
Climate+Lithology*	0.5	x								-145.09	8	322.19	4.86	2.8683	0.97
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x							-144.47	9	329.44	12.11	0.0764	0.971
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x						-144.41	10	340.24	22.92	0.0003	0.972
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x	x					-130.65	26				0.987
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x	x	x				-127.38	36				0.99
Climate+Lithology	1	Auto features								-139.30	17				0.979
Climate+Lithology*	1	x								-146.15	8	324.30	6.97	0.9994	0.97
Climate+Lithology*	1	x	x							-145.49	8	322.99	5.66	1.9215	0.97

Climate+Lithology*	1	x	x	x			-145.56	8	323.12	5.79	1.8026	0.971
Climate+Lithology	1	x	x	x	x		-142.11	10	335.66	18.33	0.0034	0.976
Climate+Lithology	1	x	x	x	x	x	-138.53	19				0.979
Climate+Lithology	1.5	Auto features					-143.29	12	372.97	55.65	0.0000	0.975
Climate+Lithology*	1.5	x					-147.40	7	319.99	2.67	8.6011	0.969
Climate+Lithology	1.5	x	x				-146.72	9	333.93	16.61	0.0081	0.969
Climate+Lithology*	1.5	x	x	x			-146.56	8	325.12	7.79	0.6620	0.97
Climate+Lithology	1.5	x	x	x	x		-145.37	10	342.16	24.84	0.0001	0.973
Climate+Lithology	1.5	x	x	x	x	x	-143.28	16	862.55	545.23	0.0000	0.975
Climate+Lithology	2	Auto features					-146.22	10	343.87	26.54	0.0001	0.971
Climate+Lithology*	2	x					-148.84	6	317.33	0.00	32.6181	0.967
Climate+Lithology	2	x	x				-147.81	8	327.63	10.30	0.1890	0.968
Climate+Lithology*	2	x	x	x			-147.66	8	327.31	9.99	0.2214	0.97
Climate+Lithology	2	x	x	x	x		-147.46	9	335.42	18.09	0.0038	0.97
Climate+Lithology	2	x	x	x	x	x	-146.38	12	379.15	61.83	0.0000	0.972
Climate+Lithology	3	Auto features					-150.02	11	366.04	48.72	0.0000	0.966
Climate+Lithology*	3	x					-152.34	5	319.68	2.35	10.0632	0.963
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x				-150.63	6	320.89	3.57	5.4768	0.965
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x	x			-150.58	7	326.37	9.04	0.3550	0.966
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x	x	x		-150.58	7	326.37	9.04	0.3552	0.966
Climate+Lithology	3	x	x	x	x	x	-150.29	11	366.57	49.25	0.0000	0.967
Climate+Lithology*	4	Auto features					-154.59	4	320.26	2.94	7.5023	0.956
Climate+Lithology*	4	x					-155.91	3	319.54	2.22	10.7669	0.954
Climate+Lithology*	4	x	x				-154.88	5	324.76	7.44	0.7914	0.955
Climate+Lithology*	4	x	x	x			-154.63	4	320.33	3.00	7.2626	0.96
Climate+Lithology*	4	x	x	x	x		-154.63	4	320.33	3.00	7.2626	0.96
Climate+Lithology	4	x	x	x	x	x	-154.00	6	327.64	10.31	0.1878	0.958

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Climate	0.5	Auto features					-248.87	41				0.904
Climate	0.5	x					-280.84	7	581.58	43.35	0.0000	0.708
Climate	0.5	x	x				-276.54	10	586.83	48.60	0.0000	0.759
Climate	0.5	x	x	x			-275.85	8	575.70	37.47	0.0000	0.766
Climate	0.5	x	x	x	x		-246.95	34				0.906
Climate	0.5	x	x	x	x	x	-240.88	40				0.928
Climate	1	Auto features					-261.67	20	703.34	165.11	0.0000	0.853
Climate	1	x					-282.36	6	580.92	42.69	0.0000	0.673
Climate	1	x	x				-278.63	9	585.84	47.61	0.0000	0.737
Climate	1	x	x	x			-277.64	7	575.18	36.95	0.0000	0.756
Climate	1	x	x	x	x		-268.68	14	600.36	62.12	0.0000	0.83
Climate	1	x	x	x	x	x	-260.22	17	622.43	84.20	0.0000	0.862
Climate	1.5	Auto features					-267.57	10	568.88	30.65	0.0000	0.822
Climate	1.5	x					-282.85	4	575.51	37.28	0.0000	0.67
Climate	1.5	x	x				-281.09	6	578.38	40.15	0.0000	0.683

Climate	1.5	x	x	x			-279.55	4	568.91	30.68	0.0000	0.732
Climate	1.5	x	x	x	x		-275.56	7	571.01	32.78	0.0000	0.79
Climate	1.5	x	x	x	x	x	-267.19	14	597.38	59.15	0.0000	0.83
Climate	2	Auto features					-271.06	11	581.73	43.49	0.0000	0.807
Climate	2	x					-283.12	4	576.05	37.82	0.0000	0.667
Climate	2	x	x				-281.63	5	576.12	37.89	0.0000	0.674
Climate	2	x	x	x			-280.46	4	570.74	32.51	0.0000	0.727
Climate	2	x	x	x	x		-278.73	4	567.28	29.05	0.0000	0.767
Climate	2	x	x	x	x	x	-270.93	9	570.44	32.21	0.0000	0.814
Climate	3	Auto features					-276.26	6	568.71	30.48	0.0000	0.758
Climate	3	x					-283.78	3	574.60	36.37	0.0000	0.648
Climate	3	x	x				-282.28	4	574.38	36.15	0.0000	0.662
Climate	3	x	x	x			-282.72	3	572.49	34.25	0.0000	0.689
Climate	3	x	x	x	x		-282.72	3	572.49	34.25	0.0000	0.689
Climate	3	x	x	x	x	x	-277.11	6	570.41	32.18	0.0000	0.776
Climate	4	Auto features					-278.93	3	564.91	26.67	0.0001	0.734
Climate	4	x					-284.15	2	572.80	34.57	0.0000	0.635
Climate	4	x	x				-283.09	3	573.23	34.99	0.0000	0.654
Climate	4	x	x	x			-284.01	2	572.51	34.28	0.0000	0.656
Climate	4	x	x	x	x		-284.01	2	572.51	34.28	0.0000	0.656
Climate	4	x	x	x	x	x	-279.44	2	563.37	25.14	0.0001	0.728
Climate+Lithology	0.5	Auto features					-228.54	41				0.935
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x					-251.69	12	549.66	11.43	0.1251	0.883
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x				-248.44	18	618.38	80.14	0.0000	0.892
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x			-249.70	17	601.41	63.18	0.0000	0.886
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x	x		-226.49	35				0.944
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x	x	x	-223.11	43				0.948
Climate+Lithology	1	Auto features					-241.27	26				0.91
Climate+Lithology	1	x					-255.01	12	556.31	18.07	0.0045	0.875
Climate+Lithology	1	x	x				-252.35	15	578.34	40.11	0.0000	0.886
Climate+Lithology*	1	x	x	x			-253.38	11	546.37	8.13	0.6501	0.876
Climate+Lithology	1	x	x	x	x		-246.26	18	614.02	75.78	0.0000	0.907
Climate+Lithology	1	x	x	x	x	x	-239.87	29				0.915
Climate+Lithology	1.5	Auto features					-246.48	19	639.52	101.29	0.0000	0.904
Climate+Lithology	1.5	x					-255.01	12	556.31	18.07	0.0045	0.875
Climate+Lithology	1.5	x	x				-256.04	12	558.36	20.13	0.0016	0.869
Climate+Lithology*	1.5	x	x	x			-256.09	10	545.93	7.70	0.8077	0.872
Climate+Lithology	1.5	x	x	x	x		-253.18	14	569.37	31.14	0.0000	0.883
Climate+Lithology	1.5	x	x	x	x	x	-246.43	17	594.86	56.63	0.0000	0.904
Climate+Lithology	2	Auto features					-250.55	14	564.11	25.88	0.0001	0.894
Climate+Lithology	2	x					-260.17	10	554.09	15.86	0.0137	0.857
Climate+Lithology	2	x	x				-258.98	12	564.24	26.00	0.0001	0.857
Climate+Lithology*	2	x	x	x			-259.01	8	542.03	3.80	5.6856	0.86
Climate+Lithology*	2	x	x	x	x		-258.28	9	545.14	6.91	1.1977	0.864

Climate+Lithology	2	x	x	x	x	x	-250.41	13	554.82	16.59	0.0095	0.894
Climate+Lithology*	3	Auto features					-255.92	9	540.42	2.19	12.6922	0.885
Climate+Lithology*	3	x					-263.69	7	547.28	9.04	0.4126	0.847
Climate+Lithology	3	x	x				-262.42	8	548.84	10.60	0.1891	0.845
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x	x			-262.69	7	545.27	7.04	1.1222	0.851
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x	x	x		-262.69	7	545.27	7.04	1.1222	0.851
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x	x	x	x	-256.20	10	546.15	7.92	0.7249	0.89
Climate+Lithology*	4	Auto features					-261.04	6	538.29	0.06	36.8840	0.862
Climate+Lithology	4	x					-267.50	6	551.21	12.98	0.0577	0.82
Climate+Lithology	4	x	x				-266.11	7	552.12	13.88	0.0367	0.835
Climate+Lithology	4	x	x	x			-266.54	6	549.28	11.05	0.1514	0.85
Climate+Lithology	4	x	x	x	x		-266.54	6	549.28	11.05	0.1514	0.85
Climate+Lithology*	4	x	x	x	x	x	-261.02	6	538.23	0.00	37.9551	0.872

Nebrioporus baeticus

Climate	0.5	Auto features					-274.25	35					0.906
Climate	0.5	x					-306.17	7	631.43	51.91	0.0000	0.742	
Climate	0.5	x	x				-302.45	10	636.48	56.96	0.0000	0.782	
Climate	0.5	x	x	x			-302.38	9	631.76	52.24	0.0000	0.783	
Climate	0.5	x	x	x	x		-273.87	33				0.913	
Climate	0.5	x	x	x	x	x	-269.47	47				0.923	
Climate	1	Auto features					-285.59	19	685.17	105.65	0.0000	0.879	
Climate	1	x					-307.10	6	629.84	50.32	0.0000	0.733	
Climate	1	x	x				-306.59	7	632.28	52.75	0.0000	0.738	
Climate	1	x	x	x			-304.25	6	624.16	44.64	0.0000	0.778	
Climate	1	x	x	x	x		-293.86	13	636.48	56.95	0.0000	0.845	
Climate	1	x	x	x	x	x	-286.24	23	802.47	222.95	0.0000	0.879	
Climate	1.5	Auto features					-290.79	12	623.93	44.41	0.0000	0.872	
Climate	1.5	x					-307.11	5	626.72	47.20	0.0000	0.739	
Climate	1.5	x	x				-306.92	5	626.35	46.83	0.0000	0.741	
Climate	1.5	x	x	x			-304.82	6	625.29	45.77	0.0000	0.78	
Climate	1.5	x	x	x	x		-299.54	6	614.74	35.22	0.0000	0.82	
Climate	1.5	x	x	x	x	x	-291.39	12	625.14	45.62	0.0000	0.871	
Climate	2	Auto features					-295.35	9	617.70	38.18	0.0000	0.848	
Climate	2	x					-307.39	6	630.43	50.91	0.0000	0.73	
Climate	2	x	x				-307.21	6	630.07	50.54	0.0000	0.733	
Climate	2	x	x	x			-306.01	5	624.52	45.00	0.0000	0.772	
Climate	2	x	x	x	x		-303.07	5	618.64	39.11	0.0000	0.801	
Climate	2	x	x	x	x	x	-296.70	10	624.99	45.47	0.0000	0.846	
Climate	3	Auto features					-300.35	7	619.80	40.28	0.0000	0.826	
Climate	3	x					-307.89	6	631.42	51.90	0.0000	0.727	
Climate	3	x	x				-307.85	5	628.19	48.67	0.0000	0.728	
Climate	3	x	x	x			-307.62	4	624.83	45.31	0.0000	0.768	
Climate	3	x	x	x	x		-307.62	4	624.83	45.31	0.0000	0.768	

Climate	3	x	x	x	x	x	-301.58	6	618.82	39.29	0.0000	0.826
Climate	4	Auto features					-305.20	7	629.50	49.97	0.0000	0.791
Climate	4	x					-308.56	6	632.78	53.26	0.0000	0.722
Climate	4	x	x				-308.72	5	629.95	50.43	0.0000	0.719
Climate	4	x	x	x			-309.34	4	628.27	48.75	0.0000	0.757
Climate	4	x	x	x	x		-309.34	4	628.27	48.75	0.0000	0.757
Climate	4	x	x	x	x	x	-307.08	6	629.81	50.29	0.0000	0.797
Climate+Lithology	0.5	Auto features					-258.22	36				0.94
Climate+Lithology*	0.5	x					-276.31	9	579.63	0.10	16.7014	0.906
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x				-275.32	15	614.93	35.41	0.0000	0.907
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x			-274.44	14	604.87	25.35	0.0001	0.908
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x	x		-256.93	29				0.945
Climate+Lithology	0.5	x	x	x	x	x	-253.00	45				0.954
Climate+Lithology	1	Auto features					-266.23	22	721.03	141.51	0.0000	0.928
Climate+Lithology*	1	x					-277.53	9	582.05	2.53	4.9700	0.907
Climate+Lithology*	1	x	x				-276.94	10	585.46	5.94	0.9031	0.907
Climate+Lithology*	1	x	x	x			-276.47	9	579.95	0.42	14.2333	0.907
Climate+Lithology	1	x	x	x	x		-271.67	14	599.34	19.82	0.0009	0.916
Climate+Lithology	1	x	x	x	x	x	-266.36	21	690.21	110.69	0.0000	0.927
Climate+Lithology	1.5	Auto features					-271.72	17	628.43	48.91	0.0000	0.918
Climate+Lithology*	1.5	x					-278.90	9	584.79	5.27	1.2608	0.906
Climate+Lithology*	1.5	x	x				-278.39	9	583.77	4.25	2.1021	0.907
Climate+Lithology*	1.5	x	x	x			-278.33	8	579.52	0.00	17.5974	0.907
Climate+Lithology*	1.5	x	x	x	x		-276.71	9	580.41	0.89	11.2784	0.909
Climate+Lithology	1.5	x	x	x	x	x	-272.56	16	618.97	39.45	0.0000	0.914
Climate+Lithology	2	Auto features					-274.03	12	590.42	10.90	0.0757	0.914
Climate+Lithology	2	x					-280.14	10	591.86	12.34	0.0368	0.907
Climate+Lithology*	2	x	x				-279.87	9	586.74	7.22	0.4770	0.907
Climate+Lithology*	2	x	x	x			-277.96	10	587.51	7.99	0.3244	0.91
Climate+Lithology	2	x	x	x	x		-279.61	10	590.80	11.28	0.0625	0.91
Climate+Lithology	2	x	x	x	x	x	-275.33	15	614.94	35.42	0.0000	0.911
Climate+Lithology	3	Auto features					-279.47	10	590.51	10.99	0.0722	0.891
Climate+Lithology*	3	x					-283.16	8	589.17	9.65	0.1412	0.886
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x				-282.96	7	585.02	5.49	1.1279	0.885
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x	x			-283.11	7	585.32	5.80	0.9693	0.886
Climate+Lithology*	3	x	x	x	x		-283.11	7	585.32	5.80	0.9693	0.886
Climate+Lithology	3	x	x	x	x	x	-280.68	12	603.71	24.19	0.0001	0.89
Climate+Lithology*	4	Auto features					-283.76	7	586.60	7.08	0.5103	0.878
Climate+Lithology*	4	x					-285.17	6	585.99	6.47	0.6920	0.874
Climate+Lithology*	4	x	x				-285.06	5	582.62	3.10	3.7345	0.874
Climate+Lithology*	4	x	x	x			-285.57	4	580.75	1.22	9.5429	0.873
Climate+Lithology*	4	x	x	x	x		-285.57	4	580.75	1.22	9.5429	0.873
Climate+Lithology*	4	x	x	x	x	x	-285.40	5	583.29	3.77	2.6735	0.873

Table S3. List of the sequenced specimens of *Enochrus falcarius* (with vouchers and accession numbers) included in the genetic analyses of this study. See Table S1 for locality codes.

Species	CodeLoc	Voucher	Accession number
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CAD	IBE-AB221	JN814761
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CAD	IBE-AB410	JN808159
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CAD	IBE-AB434	JN808161
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CAD	IBE-AB435	JN808162
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CAD	IBE-AB436	JN808163
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CAD	IBE-AB437	JN808164
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CAD	IBE-AB438	JN808165
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR2	IBE-AB369	JN808140
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR2	IBE-AB370	JN808141
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR2	IBE-AB371	JN808142
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR2	IBE-AB373	JN808143
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR2	IBE-AB374	JN808144
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR2	IBE-AB390	JN808156
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR3	IBE-AB364	JN808135
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR3	IBE-AB365	JN808136
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR3	IBE-AB366	JN808137
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR3	IBE-AB367	JN808138
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR3	IBE-AB368	JN808139
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR3	IBE-AB400	JN808157
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR3	IBE-AB401	JN808158
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	COR3	IBE-AB81	JN814805
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CUE4	IBE-AB139	JN814749
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CUE4	IBE-AB439	JN808166
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CUE4	IBE-AB440	JN808167
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CUE4	IBE-AB441	JN808168
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CUE4	IBE-AB442	JN808169
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	CUE4	IBE-AB90	JN814808
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE1	IBE-AB151	JN814750
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE1	IBE-AB152	JN808133
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE1	IBE-AB168	JN808134
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE1	IBE-AB388	JN808154
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE1	IBE-AB389	JN808155
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE1	IBE-AB80	JN814804
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE2	IBE-AB376	JN808145
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE2	IBE-AB377	JN808146
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE2	IBE-AB378	JN808147
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE2	IBE-AB387	JN808153
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE4	IBE-AB222	JN814762
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE4	IBE-AB443	JN808170
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE4	IBE-AB444	JN808171

<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE4	IBE-AB445	JN808172
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE4	IBE-AB446	JN808173
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	JAE4	IBE-AB447	JN808174
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR1	IBE-AB430	JN808160
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR1	IBE-AB453	JN808179
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR1	IBE-AB455	JN808180
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR1	IBE-AB456	JN808181
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR1	IBE-AB457	JN808182
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR11	IBE-AB381	JN808148
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR11	IBE-AB382	JN808149
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR11	IBE-AB383	JN808150
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR11	IBE-AB384	JN808151
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR11	IBE-AB386	JN808152
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR2	IBE-AB110	JN814743
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR2	IBE-AB136	JN814748
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR2	IBE-AB137	JN808127
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR2	IBE-AB138	JN808128
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR2	IBE-AB9	JN814807
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR3	IBE-AB460	JN808183
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR3	IBE-AB461	JN808184
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR3	IBE-AB462	JN808185
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR3	IBE-AB463	JN808186
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR5	IBE-AB448	JN808175
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR5	IBE-AB450	JN808176
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR5	IBE-AB451	JN808177
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR5	IBE-AB452	JN808178
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	MUR5	IBE-AB79	JN814803
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	SEV2	IBE-AB142	JN808129
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	SEV2	IBE-AB143	JN808130
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	SEV2	IBE-AB144	JN808131
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	SEV2	IBE-AB145	JN808132
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>	SEV2	IBE-AB82	JN814806

Table S4 Mismatch distribution results for a model of sudden demographic expansion for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles. Regions with samples sizes < 10 sequences are not shown. Tau (τ) was converted to thousand years ago (T ; ka) as an estimate of the time of expansion when the analysis failed to reject sudden expansion. CI, confidence interval. Codes for the main regions are as in Table 4.

Region	Sudden expansion			
	$P(\text{SSD})$	$P(\text{Rag})$	τ (95% CI)	T
<i>Ochthebius glaber</i>				
GUA	0.793	0.875	7.7 (5.4-11)	133 (93-190)
SEG	0.633	0.704	4.5 (1.2-7.7)	78 (20-133)
JUC	0.645	0.439	1.4 (0.6-2.4)	24 (10-41)
<i>Enochrus falcarius</i>				
GUA	0.000	0.975	0.0 (0.0-0.3)	--
SEG	0.187	0.273	0.6 (0.1-1.2)	10 (3-20)
<i>Ochthebius notabilis</i>				
GUA	0.474	0.762	3.8 (1.6-6)	66 (28-103)
EBR	0.427	0.639	2.9 (1-4.8)	50 (17-83)
<i>Nebrioporus baeticus</i>				
GUA	0.789	0.805	3.6 (1.8-5.2)	62 (32-90)
SEG	0.463	0.346	2.2 (1.2-3.4)	39 (21-58)
EBR	0.462	0.63	4.5 (1.2-7.2)	78 (20-125)

$P(\text{SDD})$, P -value for the sum of the squared deviations under the hypothesis of spatial expansion. $P(\text{Rag})$, P -value for the raggedness index (regions with samples sizes < 10 sequences are not shown).

Table S5 Matrices of pairwise Φ_{ST} values (bold: P -value < 0.05) between localities for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles. See Table S1 for locality codes.

Ochthebius glaber

Locality	ALI2	ALI3	CAD	COR1	COR2	COR3	CUE3	CUE4	JAE1	JAE2	JAE3	MUR10	MUR2	MUR5	MUR8	MUR9	VAL1
ALI2		0.71	0.86	0.84	0.82	0.86	0.98	0.98	0.88	0.80	0.84	0.62	0.93	0.78	0.65	0.64	0.97
ALI3	0.71		0.86	0.83	0.81	0.86	0.97	0.97	0.87	0.80	0.83	0.33	0.87	0.20	-0.10	0.15	0.97
CAD	0.86	0.86		0.38	0.44	0.46	0.91	0.91	0.35	0.31	0.39	0.83	0.91	0.88	0.84	0.83	0.91
COR1	0.84	0.83	0.38		-0.04	0.20	0.89	0.90	-0.10	-0.13	0.23	0.78	0.87	0.85	0.80	0.78	0.89
COR2	0.82	0.81	0.44	-0.04		0.16	0.88	0.88	0.08	-0.08	0.30	0.76	0.85	0.84	0.79	0.77	0.88
COR3	0.86	0.86	0.46	0.20	0.16		0.90	0.90	0.23	0.07	0.25	0.82	0.90	0.88	0.84	0.82	0.90
CUE3	0.98	0.97	0.91	0.89	0.88	0.90		-0.07	0.92	0.87	0.88	0.95	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.11
CUE4	0.98	0.97	0.91	0.90	0.88	0.90	-0.07		0.93	0.88	0.89	0.95	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.24
JAE1	0.88	0.87	0.35	-0.10	0.08	0.23	0.92	0.93		-0.05	0.20	0.82	0.91	0.89	0.84	0.83	0.92
JAE2	0.80	0.80	0.31	-0.13	-0.08	0.07	0.87	0.88	-0.05		0.20	0.76	0.84	0.82	0.77	0.76	0.87
JAE3	0.84	0.83	0.39	0.23	0.30	0.25	0.88	0.89	0.20	0.20		0.79	0.88	0.86	0.81	0.79	0.88
MUR10	0.62	0.33	0.83	0.78	0.76	0.82	0.95	0.95	0.82	0.76	0.79		0.37	0.37	0.21	0.23	0.95
MUR2	0.93	0.87	0.91	0.87	0.85	0.90	0.99	0.99	0.91	0.84	0.88	0.37		0.91	0.82	0.81	0.98
MUR5	0.78	0.20	0.88	0.85	0.84	0.88	0.98	0.98	0.89	0.82	0.86	0.37	0.91		0.08	0.16	0.97
MUR8	0.65	-0.10	0.84	0.80	0.79	0.84	0.97	0.97	0.84	0.77	0.81	0.21	0.82	0.08		0.06	0.96
MUR9	0.64	0.15	0.83	0.78	0.77	0.82	0.96	0.96	0.83	0.76	0.79	0.23	0.81	0.16	0.06		0.96
VAL1	0.97	0.97	0.91	0.89	0.88	0.90	0.11	0.24	0.92	0.87	0.88	0.95	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.96	

Enochrus falcarius

Locality	CAD	COR2	COR3	CUE4	JAE1	JAE2	JAE4	MUR1	MUR11	MUR2	MUR3	MUR5	SEV2
CAD		0.20	0.24	0.33	0.22	0.14	0.22	0.42	0.44	0.48	0.41	0.47	0.17
COR2	0.20		0.11	0.35	0.10	0.01	0.10	0.51	0.55	0.59	0.52	0.61	0.06
COR3	0.24	0.11		0.41	0.05	-0.02	0.05	0.58	0.64	0.67	0.62	0.70	-0.15
CUE4	0.33	0.35	0.41		0.60	0.53	0.60	0.10	0.12	0.40	0.11	0.16	0.46
JAE1	0.22	0.10	0.05	0.60		0.00	0.00	0.74	0.85	0.83	0.85	1.00	0.04
JAE2	0.14	0.01	-0.02	0.53	0.00		0.00	0.68	0.81	0.79	0.80	1.00	-0.05
JAE4	0.22	0.10	0.05	0.60	0.00	0.00		0.74	0.85	0.83	0.85	1.00	0.04
MUR1	0.42	0.51	0.58	0.10	0.74	0.68	0.74		0.00	0.30	-0.01	0.00	0.63
MUR11	0.44	0.55	0.64	0.12	0.85	0.81	0.85	0.00		0.11	-0.28	0.00	0.71
MUR2	0.48	0.59	0.67	0.40	0.83	0.79	0.83	0.30	0.11		-0.01	0.50	0.72
MUR3	0.41	0.52	0.62	0.11	0.85	0.80	0.85	-0.01	-0.28	-0.01		0.06	0.69
MUR5	0.47	0.61	0.70	0.16	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.06		0.83
SEV2	0.17	0.06	-0.15	0.46	0.04	-0.05	0.04	0.63	0.71	0.72	0.69	0.83	

Ochthebius notabilis

Locality	ALA	ALB1	ALB2	BUR	COR2	GRA	GUA1	HUE	JAE1	LER	MUR7	SEV2
ALA		0.77	0.64	0.27	0.72	0.35	0.62	0.56	0.53	0.81	0.85	0.70
ALB1	0.77		0.76	0.94	0.80	0.70	0.90	0.79	0.55	0.96	0.92	0.80
ALB2	0.64	0.76		0.75	0.69	0.54	0.50	0.69	0.44	0.88	0.85	0.67
BUR	0.27	0.94	0.75		0.83	0.33	1.00	0.62	0.56	1.00	0.94	0.81
COR2	0.72	0.80	0.69	0.83		0.44	0.73	0.72	-0.02	0.89	0.86	-0.07
GRA	0.35	0.70	0.54	0.33	0.44		0.45	0.50	0.31	0.72	0.78	0.46
GUA1	0.62	0.90	0.50	1.00	0.73	0.45		0.69	0.33	1.00	0.92	0.70
HUE	0.56	0.79	0.69	0.62	0.72	0.50	0.69		0.58	0.45	0.83	0.72
JAE1	0.53	0.55	0.44	0.56	-0.02	0.31	0.33	0.58		0.73	0.73	-0.10
LER	0.81	0.96	0.88	1.00	0.89	0.72	1.00	0.45	0.73		0.96	0.89
MUR7	0.85	0.92	0.85	0.94	0.86	0.78	0.92	0.83	0.73	0.96		0.86
SEV2	0.70	0.80	0.67	0.81	-0.07	0.46	0.70	0.72	-0.10	0.89	0.86	

Nebrioporus baeticus

Locality	ALA	CAD	COR3	CUE1	GUA1	GUA3	HUE	JAE1	MUR1	MUR3	MUR4	MUR5	NAV1	SEV1	SEV2	ZAR1
ALA		0.71	0.60	0.97	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.67	0.79	0.87	0.82	0.83	0.47	0.56	0.58	0.96
CAD	0.71		0.27	0.68	0.39	0.50	0.53	-0.04	0.09	0.13	0.26	0.02	0.12	0.04	0.08	0.63
COR3	0.60	0.27		0.68	0.50	0.58	0.50	0.12	0.41	0.41	0.35	0.36	0.02	0.06	-0.03	0.58
CUE1	0.97	0.68	0.68		1.00	1.00	1.00	0.66	0.73	0.87	0.79	0.79	0.65	0.54	0.59	1.00
GUA1	0.95	0.39	0.50	1.00		0.00	1.00	0.39	0.44	0.67	0.56	0.50	0.42	0.30	0.33	1.00
GUA3	0.96	0.50	0.58	1.00	0.00		1.00	0.50	0.55	0.76	0.68	0.63	0.53	0.42	0.45	1.00
HUE	0.95	0.53	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.00		0.51	0.68	0.80	0.73	0.70	0.28	0.36	0.39	0.00
JAE1	0.67	-0.04	0.12	0.66	0.39	0.50	0.51		0.13	0.15	0.26	0.14	0.07	-0.01	-0.03	0.61
MUR1	0.79	0.09	0.41	0.73	0.44	0.55	0.68	0.13		-0.20	0.21	-0.01	0.29	0.18	0.21	0.75
MUR3	0.87	0.13	0.41	0.87	0.67	0.76	0.80	0.15	-0.20		0.22	0.06	0.27	0.17	0.17	0.86
MUR4	0.82	0.26	0.35	0.79	0.56	0.68	0.73	0.26	0.21	0.22		0.22	0.29	0.18	0.11	0.81
MUR5	0.83	0.02	0.36	0.79	0.50	0.63	0.70	0.14	-0.01	0.06	0.22		0.21	0.10	0.16	0.79
NAV1	0.47	0.12	0.02	0.65	0.42	0.53	0.28	0.07	0.29	0.27	0.29	0.21		-0.06	-0.04	0.41
SEV1	0.56	0.04	0.06	0.54	0.30	0.42	0.36	-0.01	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.10	-0.06		-0.08	0.48
SEV2	0.58	0.08	-0.03	0.59	0.33	0.45	0.39	-0.03	0.21	0.17	0.11	0.16	-0.04	-0.08		0.50
ZAR1	0.96	0.63	0.58	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.61	0.75	0.86	0.81	0.79	0.41	0.48	0.50	

Figure S1 Species distribution modelling predictions for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles for the present (left) and the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM, right) obtained with the Mahalanobis distance approach. Warmer colours represent areas of higher habitat suitability. Mahalanobis distances were converted into probability values according to the χ^2 distribution.

Figure S2 The observed pairwise differences and the expected mismatch distributions under a sudden expansion model and a spatial expansion model for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles in the different regions with samples sizes > 10 sequences.

Figure S3 Maps of cumulative habitat resistance for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles for present (left) and LGM (right) scenarios. The gradient of colours indicates the probability of species movement, with warmer colours representing high habitat connectivity.

Figure 1 Species distribution modelling predictions for the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles for the present (left) and the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM, right) obtained with Maxent. Warmer colours represent areas of higher habitat suitability. Black points represent present-day occurrence data used in the modelling. The percentage of the summed habitat suitability at the LGM relative to the present is also indicated. The insert shows the position of the study area in the Mediterranean Basin.
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Figure 2 Comparison between present and Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) potential ranges and phylogenetic relationships among mtDNA haplotypes of the four species of Iberian saline-habitat water beetles (statistical parsimony networks). Shaded areas correspond to suitable areas: dark grey, stable areas (i.e., suitable during both time periods); light grey, present distributional areas predicted to have been unsuitable during the LGM; and black, currently unsuitable areas predicted to have been suitable during the LGM. The boundaries of the main river basins are indicated by green lines. Populations used in genetic analyses are shown in the maps with colour circles (different colours represent the different main regions: blue, Guadalquivir; orange, Segura; green, Júcar; red, Ebro; yellow, Gadiana; purple, Tajo). In COI haplotype networks, solid lines connect haplotypes with a single step (missing intermediates are indicated by small open circles). Circle diameter is proportional to the number of individuals. White haplotypes in *Ochthebius notabilis* correspond to Moroccan populations.

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